

SURVEILLANCE CARD_Influenza in Swine_Pathogen detection in pigs with clinical signs

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Pathogen detection in pigs with clinical signs.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of an increase in incidence, i.e., early epidemic detection. Early detection of newly emerging influenza strains with increased virulence / pathogenicity in pigs and potentially humans. Mapping SIV strains circulating in the country.
3	Target species and group	Pigs with clinical symptoms.
4	Target sector / production type	All sectors and production types.
5	Geographical area covered	Whole country.
6	Age group	All age groups.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Virological surveillance targeted to all pig farms where a high incidence of acute respiratory symptoms was observed. The selection criterium for individuals within this target population is that the animal shows clinical signs of acute respiratory disease. To reach a high coverage of pig farms with acute respiratory disease, this surveillance component could be accompanied by a disease awareness campaign. During these campaigns, also the threshold incidence that should trigger action should be communicated.
8	Sampling time period	Year-round as SIV infection is maintained in endemic cycles without clear seasonality.
9	Sampling matrix	Nasal secretion and mucosa collected with a swab. In addition, in cases of mortality, tissue samples from the lungs and/or the upper respiratory tract could be used for virus detection (1).
10	Type of disease indicators	Antigen detection (RNA virus).
11	Sampling unit	Nasal swabs are taken from individual pigs showing respiratory disease (no pooling).

		In addition, chewing ropes can be used to sample (pooled) saliva.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	A sample of sick pigs (main symptom: cough and fever) are swabbed, targeting at least 3 animals with the most pronounced clinical symptoms.
13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	<p>Clinical material is screened using PCR.</p> <p>For more detailed analysis, clinical materials are cultured in either cells or embryonated fowl's eggs. Several tools are available for virus characterisation, including standard typing through haemagglutination inhibition test (HI) and/or RT-PCR or subtyping by genome sequencing. With real time RT-PCRs influenza A viruses known to be endemic in European pigs plus emergent strains from North America can be detected (1).</p>
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	<p>The design prevalence will vary between countries.</p> <p>During the ESNIP 3 project phase (2010 – 2013), a total of 8977 pig herds were examined in 17 countries. Influenza A virus could be detected in 2742 herds (30.5% positive) (1).</p>
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	To be defined, ideally 95%.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	Whole genome sequencing of the identified SIV and comparison with isolates from humans and other animals provides information how animal genome sequences relate to the viruses circulating in humans.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Avian influenza virus, Ebola virus, MERS virus, Nipah virus and pathogens causing respiratory disease in general.
18	References	1) ESNIP (European Surveillance Network for Influenza in Pigs), 2013. Project 259949 – Final Technical Report (December 2013). Available online: https://cordis.europa.eu/docs/results/259/259949/final1-template-for-final-report-esnip-3-.pdf .